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Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Psychological Well-being Among IT Professionals

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to investigate the relationship between job satisfaction and psychological well-being among IT professionals. It was hypothesized that there will be a positive relationship between job satisfaction and psychological well-being. This study was carried out on IT professional in Pune city, India. A total of 70 IT professional were selected by simple random sampling technique. Psychological Well-Being Scale developed by Ryff (2014), Job Satisfaction Scale developed by Amar Singh and T.R. Sharma (1999), and a Personal information questionnaire were used as data collection tools in the present research. Data was statistically analyzed using product moment r . The study has found a moderate positive relationship ($r=0.409^{**}$) between psychological well-being and job satisfaction, it was also found that 36% IT professionals was extremely satisfied with their job.

Keywords

Psychological Well-being, Job Satisfaction, IT Professionals, Psychological Well-being Scale by Ryff, Job Satisfaction Scale by Amar Singh and T.R. Sharma.

Introduction

The information technology (IT) sector in India is one of the key service industries. IT industry is growing to be a significant global employer and driver of development, with a clear route to increased global competitiveness, enhanced protective skills, and among other things, the resolution of energy and environmental challenges. Pune is regarded as India's IT hub and offers significant career prospects to IT specialists. Therefore, it is necessary to study psychological well-being and job satisfaction of employees in IT sector in Pune.

Psychological well-being is the quality of life that consists of peacefulness, gladness, accomplishment and satisfaction of individuals in their life (Ryff, 1991). Psychological well-being is also the cognitive assessment of individuals on their satisfaction with entire life and it is mixture of mental, physical, social and emotional aspects of individuals (Kaur, 2013). It is the combination of feeling good and functioning effectively. Psychological well-being consists of positive relationships with others, personal mastery, autonomy, a feeling of purpose and meaning in life, and personal growth and development. Psychological well-being is attained by achieving a state of balance affected by both challenging and rewarding life events.

The concept of job satisfaction that was firstly defined and measured by Taylor in 1911 was associated with economic income provided from job and rewards occupations provided to individuals (Çetin & Özcan, 2004). Luthans emphasized job satisfaction as including various dimensions such as salary and promotion (Toker, 2011). When the definition of job satisfaction concept is investigated, it is possible to consider that job satisfaction is an expression of employees' psychological health.

Present paper offers a precise way to find out the relationship between job satisfaction and psychological wellbeing among IT professionals. Since there is a smaller number of studies conducted on IT professionals with reference to job satisfaction and psychological well-being, this study is a small contribution toward it. Enhancing well-being in the workplace accelerate performance and profitability by having employees who are psychologically healthy and happy at workplace. Enhancing the job satisfaction of employee at work will be

beneficial for the employees as it makes a difference to their working life and helps in the success of organization.

Aim of study

The purpose of this research was to investigate the relationship between job satisfaction and psychological well-being among IT professionals.

1. To examine the relationship between job satisfaction and psychological well-being among IT professionals.

2. To examine the level of job satisfaction and psychological well-being among IT professionals.

Review of Literature

There is limited evidence of relationship between job satisfaction and psychological wellbeing among IT professionals in India. This research is one of the very few that has been made from the perspective of employees in IT sector.

Wright et al. (2000) conducted a study on psychological well-being and job satisfaction as predictors of job performance on human services workers employed by a northern California country agency (N=47). Results indicated that there is a positive correlation between job satisfaction and psychological well-being.

Shanmugam et al. (2019) conducted a study on Psychological Well Being and Job Satisfaction of Employees in Information Technology (IT) Sector in Coimbatore district and found that psychological well-being has positive, significant and high relation with job satisfaction of employees in IT sector.

Rajeswari et al. (2017) conducted a Study on Psychological Well-Being among Employees of I.T Companies and revealed that the people with high levels of satisfaction and motivation will display a positive attitude and cheerfulness.

Many other studies have explored the relationship between job satisfaction and psychological well-being on other sectors also. Mallika, N. (2010) conducted a study on the relationship between job satisfaction and demographical variable. Results indicates that Around 60% employee among the total population has the high level of job satisfaction. the demographic variables such as gender, age, educational qualification, experience, marital status, and income significantly influence the job satisfaction perception of employees.

Sinha et. al. (2013) conducted Study of Job Satisfaction of the Employees of Private Sector Banks and found that 64.44% employees of private sector banks are satisfied while 35.56% respondents are dissatisfied from their job.

Bashir et al. (2015) conducted a study on Psychological Well-Being among Public and Private Undertakings in Aligarh and found that over all psychological well-being of public undertakings is higher than private undertakings.

Wadhawan (2016) studied on psychological well-being as a predictor to job performance and job satisfaction and revealed that positive and significant relation was prevailed among employees. If psychological well-being of employees was higher, their satisfaction towards job was also high and they were happy to work in the organization.

Baruti and Gwandure (2017) concluded that significant and positive relation existed among psychological well beings of employees and their satisfaction towards jobs and psychological well beings forecasted job satisfaction not commitment of employees.

Sampling

Sample for the present study consisted of 70 IT professionals from different IT company in India. Simple random sampling technique was used for the sample selection.

Tools Used

Following tools were used in this study;

Personal Data Questionnaire:

The questionnaire was prepared by the authors to obtain information about respondent name, age, sex, socio economic status, etc.

Psychological well-being:

In this research psychological well-being scale developed by Ryff (2014) was used. The scale consists of 42 items. Which consists a series of statement reflecting the six areas of psychological well- being: self-acceptance, positive relation with others, autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life and personal growth. Respondents rate statement on a scale of 1 to 6, with 1 indicating strong disagreement and 6 indicating strong agreement. The internal consistency coefficients of the scale between 0.86 and 0.93.

Job satisfaction scale:

A standardized test Job Satisfaction Scale (JSS) developed by Dr. Amar Singh and Dr. T.R. Sharma (1999) was used for the study. The JSS comprises 30 items of which 24 are positive and remaining 6 are negative statements. It has lowest score of 47 or below which indicates extremely dissatisfied and the high score of 74 or above indicates extremely satisfied.

Statistics Used in the Study

Data was statistically analyzed using product moment r.

Result and Discussion

The present study consists of total 70 IT professionals from Pune city of India. Respondents in this study, 67% (n=47) were male, with females comprising 33% (n=23). To explore relationship between job satisfaction and psychological well-being among IT professionals, the result were statistically analyze using Pearson Product movement 'r'.

Observation table-1 Showing Relationship between job satisfaction and Psychological Well Being

Particulars	Correlation coefficient
Psychological Well Being and Job Satisfaction of Employees in IT Sector	0.409**

Source: Primary Data

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

Observation table no. 1 shows moderate positive correlation between job satisfaction and psychological well-being. The values of Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) have been found 0.409** that indicate a moderate tendency of one variable to increase or decrease together with another variable. Which means if job satisfaction among IT professionals will increase the level of psychological well-being will also increase and vice versa.

Figure no.1 scatter plot between job satisfaction and psychological well being

Observation table no. 2 showing level of Job satisfaction among IT professionals

Level of Job satisfaction	Total sample	
	N	%
Extremely satisfied	25	36%
Very satisfied	21	30%
Moderately satisfied	14	20%
Not satisfied	6	8%
Extremely dissatisfied	4	6%

Total	70	100%
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Source: Primary Data

Observation table no. 2 shows the prevalence of job satisfaction among IT professionals. Table indicates that 36% employees are extremely satisfied with their job and 30% employees are very satisfied with their job. Only 6% employees are extremely dissatisfied with their job among the total sample. Hence it is clear that prevalence of job satisfaction varies among IT professionals.

Figure no. 2 showing level of job satisfaction among IT professionals

Observation table no.3 showing Prevalence of psychological well-being among IT professionals

Level of Psychological well being	N(Percentage)
Low Level	18.58%
Moderate Level	48.57%
High Level	32.85%

Source: Primary Data

The observation table no.3 indicates the level of psychological well-being among IT professionals. With reference to the manual there are no specific scores or cut-points for defining high or low well-being. Those distinctions can be derived from distributional information from the data collected. Hence data has been analyzed using quartile analysis. It has been found that score of 142 represents 25th percentile (Q1) below which all the scores are low well-being scores. Similarly, score of 169 represents 75th percentile (Q3) above which all the scores are high well-being scores. All the scores between 142 and 169 represents Q2 which indicate moderate level of PWB.

The observation table no. 3 indicates that there is moderate level of psychological well-being among IT professionals. 48.57% employees have moderate level of psychological well-being and only 32.85% employee has high level of psychological well-being where as 18.58% employees has low level of psychological well-being. Majority of the population falls under the criteria of moderate level of psychological well-being. It can be concluded that there is a smaller number of employees with high psychological well being hence there is a strong need to improve the level of psychological well-being among IT professionals.

Figure no.3 showing level of job satisfaction among IT professionals

Discussion

The present study consists of total 70 IT professionals from different IT companies of Pune city. The main objective of the study was to examine the relationship between job satisfaction and psychological well-being among IT professionals. It was found that there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and psychological well-being thus H1 that there will be a positive relationship between job satisfaction and psychological well-being was also accepted. The results of this study are consistent with previous researches of Wright et al. (2000); Wadhawan (2016); Baruti and Gwandure (2017); Shanmugam et al. (2019).

H2: The level of job satisfaction and PWB will vary among IT professionals.

It was found that 36% IT professionals were extremely satisfied with their job. 30% employee among the entire sample was found very satisfied with their job where as 6% employee was found extremely dissatisfied with their job. It indicates that most of the IT professionals are extremely satisfied with their job. similar to the research findings. The level of psychological well-being among IT professionals was found moderate. There were only 32.85% employees who have high level of psychological well-being. High psychological well-being is about feeling happy and doing well. People with high psychological well-being report feeling capable, happy, well supported and satisfied with life. Studies have discovered that people with higher psychological well-being are more likely to live healthier and longer lives. They are also more likely to enjoy a better quality of life. Better psychological well-being also is associated with fewer social problems. Rajeswari et al. (2017) have also found the similar results. Hence IT companies need to improve the level of psychological well-being among employees in Pune city.

Conclusion

From the results of this study, it can be concluded that there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and psychological well-being of employees in IT sector of Pune city. In addition, job satisfaction levels and psychological well-being levels vary among IT professional but the satisfaction related to job has been found extremely satisfied with the job and level of psychological well-being is moderate among employee. Thus, policies and practices should focus on improving level of psychological well-being to create an enjoyable environment with important duties to perform and to have a happy mental and physical health life.

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